

SECTION OF HISTORICAL SCIENCES

PATRONAGE IN KAZAKHSTAN IN THE 19TH - BEGINNING OF THE 20TH CENTURIES.

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Abstract

Patronage activities in the XIX - early XX centuries. played an important role in the development of social and cultural institutions, especially in the fields of art, education, science and culture. The authors seek to consider various aspects of the development of patronage in Kazakhstan. Particular attention is paid to Islam, which in the principles of religion emphasizes the importance of supporting and helping those in need, and also encourages the promotion of education, culture and charity. To solve the tasks set, various methods are used, such as a theoretical analysis of literature, a comparative historical method, an axiological approach. The study takes into account modern trends and ideas in the humanities and integrates them in the analysis of patronage activities. This allows us to present this phenomenon in the context of its relevance and significance for modern society.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, patronage, charity, Islamic traditions, culture, education.

Introduction

In the period from the middle of the 19th to the beginning of the 20th century, patronage played an important role in the development and support of various areas of culture and art. Patrons voluntarily and free of charge provide assistance to achieve social or cultural goals, contributing to the development of various areas of life and culture. It should be noted that patronage and charity are two different approaches to providing financial or other support for the benefit of society or specific social and cultural projects. Despite the fact that both of these concepts are associated with acts of voluntary assistance, they have different purposes and characteristics. Patronage is a form of sponsorship provided by individuals, firms, or organizations to advance and support the arts, science, education, culture, and other public causes. Patrons tend to support creative people or projects that have cultural or educational value, as well as contribute to public good. They can finance the creation of works of art, the construction of cultural centers, universities, scientific research. Patronage is often associated with the development of society as a whole and the promotion of cultural heritage.

Charity is an act of voluntary assistance given to people who are in need or are in a difficult life situation. Charity aims to help the poor, the sick, children, the elderly, the disabled, victims of disasters and others in need. The main goal of charity is to provide assistance and support to those who are unable to provide themselves with the minimum necessities of life. Donations can be made both financially and in the form of material resources or the provision of free services. Philanthropy is focused on supporting culture, education, and social good, while charity is focused on helping people in need and ensuring social well-being. "Patronage (lat. - a rich patron) is a type of voluntary gratuitous material assistance to cultural figures, cultural institutions and actions from wealthy and influential patrons. Patronage contributes to the development of culture, the identification and cultivation of talents. It is selective, and therefore represents a certain order and social control

on the part of some consumers. The motives of patronage can be very different: love for art, memory of the past, gratitude for support, "for the soul" and for the sake of saving the soul, etc. The word "patronage" comes from the name of the Roman political figure Maecenas Caius Tullius (I century BC. H.) - the patron of arts and sciences. Today, such disinterested help is called sponsorship" [1].

In general, it must be said that patronage, as a form of charity and sponsorship, provided financial or material support to various social, cultural, scientific, educational projects and programs.

Research methods

Important for the study of philanthropic activities is the analysis of cultural, philosophical, sociological, historical and economic literature. This provides an opportunity to comprehend the theoretical foundations of patronage and understand its place and role in culture and society. The comparative-historical method is used to consider various forms of philanthropic activity at different stages of its development. Comparison of historical contexts and traditions makes it possible to identify general patterns and features of the development of patronage in various sociocultural conditions.

The axiological approach helps to consider philanthropic activity as a significant social value. Evaluative aspects make it possible to understand what values and ideals patrons support and how their activities affect the formation of the cultural values of society.

Discussion

In the monograph "Patrons of Education" S. Leckey examines the history of the founding of the educational society in the Russian Empire in 1765 under the auspices of Catherine the Great. [2]. This society published the Proceedings of the Free Economic Society and was considered a model for social activity and initiative in tsarist Russia. Such educational societies, in particular the Free Economic Society, played an important role in promoting the cultural and scientific development of the Russian Empire. They contributed to the development of education, science, enlightenment

and culture, supported scientists, writers, artists, initiated the publication of books and magazines, and held scientific and educational events [3].

According to Myrzykhanov E.N. in understanding the driving motives in the provision of philanthropic activities, it is necessary to pay attention to the religious identity of philanthropists. "It is of great interest in understanding the movement of philanthropists and patrons to study the motives that motivated entrepreneurs to patronize and charitable activities. There are various points of view on the motivations for such charity in the literature. In the pre-revolutionary period, the high religiosity of the bourgeoisie and merchants was considered the main reason for patronage and charity" [4].

Aspects of the social life of the Kazakhs, including their participation in cultural events, charity concerts and educational institutions, could be carefully hidden in the official biographies of Kazakh cultural figures before the revolution due to persecution and repression. "Many of the cultural figures even before the revolution were educated in Muslim madrasahs, participated in charity concerts. However, these facts were carefully concealed in their official biographies in order to avoid persecution" [5]. Because of this, some facts about their participation in cultural life and educational institutions were hidden or hushed up in official biographies in order to avoid unpleasant consequences.

Results

Patrons contributed to the development of education by supporting universities, schools and scientific research. They helped create scholarships and funds for students and scholars. Many patrons were involved in charity, helping the needy and supporting various public projects. Patronage can take various forms and manifestations:

- Cultural patronage: support for artists, writers, musicians, theaters, galleries, museums and other cultural research and projects.
- Educational patronage: funding of educational institutions, scholarships, programs and research projects.
- Scientific patronage: financial support for scientific research, research institutes and programs.
- Social patronage: assistance to public organizations that are engaged in charity, social programs, helping those in need, etc.

During the period of colonial rule of the imperial system in the Russian Empire, Turkic-Muslim peoples such as Tatars, Bashkirs, Turkmens, Uzbeks and others faced problems in relations with the metropolis and the dominant culture.

The cultural policy of the empire also had a colonial connotation. Turkic-Muslim culture and education did not receive proper recognition and support, and in some cases were subjected to repression and assimilation efforts.

At the beginning of the 20th century, a stormy national awakening arose among the Turkic-Muslim peoples, which was expressed in the desire for self-determination, the protection of their rights and interests, as well as the restoration and development of their own culture and education.

This movement led to the creation of national intellectual and educational organizations, the publication of literature in native languages, the development of schools and universities with national educational content.

Patronage, or the support and sponsorship of the arts, education, charitable causes, and community initiatives, has a long and significant history in Islam. The main aspects inherent in patronage in Islam are the following:

- zakat, one of the five pillars of Islam, obligatory duty for Muslims. Zakat is an obligatory annual payment of 2.5% of a Muslim's excess wealth. This payment is intended to help the needy, the poor, orphans and other socially vulnerable segments of society [6].
- Saadaka, voluntary donations and alms, which Muslims can do at their discretion. Sadaka can be used to help the needy, build mosques, education, charity projects and other good deeds.
- wahf, a form of patronage in which wealthy people or families donated their property values (real estate, land, money, etc.) for a public good, such as mosques, schools, hospitals, public baths, etc. These properties became the property of the society and was used in accordance with the instructions of the patron [7].

Patronage in Islam plays an important role in the development of society, education and culture. It contributes to the fight against poverty and inequality, promotes the creation of cultural and educational centers, and promotes the development of art and science. In the Islamic tradition, philanthropy is seen as a good deed and service to society.

"At the end of the 19th – beginning of the 20th century, Kazakh patronage was greatly developed, the most famous in the Kazakh steppe were the names of the Kunanbaevs, Kazangapovs, Nurikenovs, Shormanovs, Khalbins, Kosshygulovs, Zhetysu bays Mamanovs and Turusbekovs" [8].

It should also be noted the role of patronage of M. Zhumabaev, S. Seifullin and many other representatives of the Kazakh intellectual elite, who contributed to the creation and dissemination of national culture and education.

Conclusion

Thus, history is rich in examples of patronage in the field of culture and art. Wealthy rulers, intellectual elites, entrepreneurs, and merchants often sponsored the construction of mosques, madrasahs (educational institutions), libraries, and also supported artists, poets, and scientists. However, it should be noted that philanthropic activity at that time was not as widespread as it is now. At that time, the society was focused on other priorities, and many charitable activities could be associated with religious or public organizations.

In general, patronage activities in the mid-19th and early 20th centuries in Kazakhstan played an important role in the development of education, culture and art, contributing to the preservation and development of national and cultural identity.

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